

THE FAILURE OF COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL
SHELLS WITH CIRCULAR HOLES UNDER
INTERNAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Graphite/epoxy cylinders with holes were tested. Holes of varying diameters were drilled through the wall of cylindrical shell with diamond-sand drills. Patches covering the holes were installed on the inner surfaces of shells and sealed with sealant. A simple method was developed to predict the failure pressure of cylinders with holes. A comparison of the predicted values with test data shows that the method is reasonable.

INTRODUCTION

In composite structures, there are some cylindrical shells with holes such as bolt-holes, inspection holes, windows in fuselages.

The failure problem of plates with holes was investigated by many authors, especially Mar, J.W. and Lin, K.Y. [1]. Mar-Lin relationship was suggested to estimate the failure stress of plates with holes. However, we must pay close attention to composite cylinders with holes to meet the needs

of engineering. In present work, the failure problem of composite cylindrical shells was investigated experimentally and theoretically. Experimental data have been obtained on the pressure required to cause the rapid failure. A estimate approach was developed to extend the Mar-Lin relationship of a flat sheet to the cylinders with holes. The estimate results are in agreement with the experimental data.

EXPERIMENT

The laminated cylinders were fabricated of Hercules A370-5H/3501=6 graphite/epoxy cloth prepreg. The stacking sequence oriented the two inner plies with their filaments at +/- 45 deg and the two outer plies with their filaments at 0 and 90 deg to the longitudinal axis of the cylinders. Fabrication was accomplished on a 12 in. diam aluminum mandrel. The autoclave cure was a two step process with the first step at 240 °F for 1 h and the second stage at 350 °F for 2 h. After removal from mendrel, the cylindrical shell was postcured in an oven at 350 °F for 8 h.

Holes were drilled through the wall of cylindrical shell using diamond-sand drills. The edges of the holes are smooth and slippery. The patches covering the holes were installed on the inner surfaces and sealed with sealant so that it became pressure tight.

The aluminum end caps were bonded onto the two ends of the shell. In this way, it became possible to monotonically increase the pressure until rapid failure occurred. The failure pressure can be uniquely determined.

Four specimens were tested. They are 24 inches long and have a diameter of 12 inches. The circular holes are located in the middle of the cylinders. Testing took place in a large blast chamber. Pressure was applied with nitrogen. The pressure was measured with a transducer and recorded with a plotter. The strains were measured with strain gages. Data acquisition was performed by a PDP-11 computer. The pressures which caused catastrophic failure are shown in Table 1.

ESTIMATE APPROACH

In present work, we pursued an approximate approach to satisfy the request of engineering application. For calculating the failure pressure of the quasi-isotropic laminated cylinders, we consider an isotropic plate with a circular hole and an isotropic cylinder with a hole. If failure of a plate occurs at the far field stress σ_{plate} , the maximum tangential stress around the hole should be $(\sigma_a)_{plate}$ at point a. (Fig 2) It can be assumed that a cylinder should fail if the maximum stress around the hole in the cylinder $(\sigma_a)_{cyl}$ reach to $(\sigma_a)_{plate}$, i.e.

$$(\sigma_a)_{cyl} = (\sigma_a)_{plate} \quad (1)$$

$(\sigma_a)_{cyl}$ and $(\sigma_a)_{plate}$ can be expressed as

$$(\sigma_a)_{plate} = C_p \sigma_{plate} \quad (2)$$

$$(\sigma_a)_{cyl} = C_c \sigma_{hoop} \quad (3)$$

C_p is stress concentration factor for plate, equal to 3 usually. C_c is stress concentration factor for cylinder, deduced from [2]. Consequently, we can estimate the failure hoop stress approximately by following formula.

$$\sigma_{hoop} = \frac{1}{K_{hole}} \sigma_{plate} \quad (4)$$

and

$$K_{hole} = C_c / C_p \quad (5)$$

where

σ_{hoop} : failure hoop stress in cylinder

σ_{plate} : failure stress in plate

K_{hole} : curvature coefficient

σ_{plate} can be obtained from Mar-Lin relationship

$$\sigma_{plate} = H_c (2a)^{-0.28} \quad (6)$$

where

H_c : composite fracture toughness

a : radius of hole in cylinder

A curve of K_{hole} versus λ is plotted in Fig.3. K_{slit} shown in Fig.3 denotes the curvature coefficient of cylinder with slit. K_{hole} is the same as K_{slit} if $\lambda \leq 3.677$. [3]

$$K_{\text{hole}} = (1 + 0.317\lambda^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

for $\lambda \leq 3.677$

K_{hole} can be approximately expressed as follows if $\lambda > 3.677$.

$$K_{\text{hole}} = b_1 + b_2\lambda + b_3\lambda^2 \quad (8)$$

for $\lambda > 3.677$

and

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{a^2(12(1-\nu^2))^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Rh} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= 0.532 \\ b_2 &= 0.696 \\ b_3 &= -0.0586 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and

- λ : curvature parameter
- ν : Poisson's ratio
- R : radius of cylinder
- h : thickness of cylinder wall

Finally, the failure pressure is able to be calculated by

$$P_{\text{cal}} = \frac{h}{R} \sigma_{\text{hoop}} \quad (11)$$

The calculation results for specimens are shown in Table 1.

DISCUSSION

A comparison of test data with calculation results shows that the estimate approach presented here is reasonable to predict the failure pressure of composite cylinders with circular holes.

It can be found out from Fig.3 that the curve K_{hole} is lower than K_{slit} if λ is larger than 3.677. Therefore, the failure pressure of cylinders with holes is higher than that

with slits for the same value of λ . It is caused by the phenomena that the bulging effect in cylinders with slits is more serious and cutting a hole can reduce the effect. As a result, the failure pressure for cylinders with holes is higher than that with slits.

Table 1
Test data and estimate results

No. of cyl.	Diameter of hole (in)	λ	K_{hole}	P_{test} (MPA)	P_{cal} (MPA)
1	2	3.151	2.037	1.721	1.140
2	2	3.151	2.037	1.138	1.140
3	2.5	3.937	2.365	1.034	0.930
4	3	4.726	2.514	0.826	0.833

$$H_c = 763 \text{ MPA}(\text{mm})^{-0.28}$$

$$\gamma = 0.315$$

Fig. 1. Cylindrical shell with hole

Fig. 2. Maximum stresses causing failure in plate and cylinder

Fig. 3. Curvature coefficients K_{hole} and K_{slit}

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